

A comparative study of dry-coated fumed metal oxides for enhanced cycling performance of SiO_x/C anodes in lithium-ion batteries

Ana L. Azevedo Costa^{a,b}, Mareike Liebertseder^a, Tatiana Gambaryan-Roisman^b, Daniel Esken^a, Frank Menzel^a

^a Evonik Operations GmbH, Rodenbacher Chaussee 4, Hanau, 63457, Germany

^b Institute for Technical Thermodynamics, Technische Universität Darmstadt, Peter-Grünberg-Straße 10, Darmstadt, 64287, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Silicon (Si) is a promising anode material for next-generation lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) due to its high theoretical capacity. However, its practical application is hindered by significant volume changes during cycling, leading to particle pulverization, loss of electrical contact, and rapid capacity fading. To address these challenges, we study the effect of dry particle coating with nanostructured fumed metal oxides (TiO₂, MgO, ZrO₂, and Al₂O₃) on enhancing the electrochemical performance of SiO_x/C anodes. The dry coating process, a facile and scalable technique, effectively attaches the metal oxide nanoparticles onto the SiO_x/C surface, forming a protective layer. The coated anode active materials (AAMs) exhibit improved cycling stability and rate capability compared to the uncoated SiO_x/C, with the Al₂O₃-coated anode demonstrating the most promising overall performance. The effective and uniform distribution of the porous coating acts as a protective layer, reducing side reactions while simultaneously enhancing ion diffusion kinetics and improving electrolyte accessibility. Detailed characterization reveals that the Al₂O₃ coating promotes the controlled formation of a LiF-rich solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer, contributing to enhanced ionic conductivity and stability. This study highlights the potential of dry particle coating with different metal oxides as a promising strategy for developing high-performance Si-based anodes for next-generation LIBs.

1. Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have emerged as the dominant energy storage technology, powering everything from portable electronics to electric vehicles, due to their high energy and power density, long lifespan, and relatively low environmental impact compared to other commercial options [1–3]. However, the ever-increasing energy demands of modern society necessitate the development of LIBs with even greater energy and power capabilities.

Silicon (Si) has garnered significant attention as a promising anode material for next-generation LIBs due to its exceptionally high theoretical capacity — approximately ten times that of conventional graphite anodes [4–7]. This, combined with its natural abundance, low cost, and non-toxicity, makes Si a compelling alternative to traditional anode materials [8–10]. Despite these advantages, significant challenges hinder the practical application of Si-based anodes. The most critical issue is the substantial volume change (up to 300%) that Si undergoes during lithiation and delithiation, which induces severe mechanical stress. This stress leads to electrode degradation,

particle pulverization, and loss of electrical contact, ultimately resulting in capacity fade [5,7]. Additionally, the continuous formation and reformation of the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer irreversibly consume lithium ions, further exacerbating capacity loss [5, 11,12]. The inherently low electronic conductivity and lithium-ion diffusivity of Si also limit its rate capability [5]. To address these challenges, various strategies have been explored, including nanostructuring, composite materials, and advanced electrolyte formulations. One particularly promising approach involves engineering interfacial coatings that mimic the properties of the SEI layer [7,13]. By pre-coating Si surfaces with materials that resemble the SEI, the irreversible capacity loss associated with SEI formation can be minimized. Ideal coatings should be ionically conductive, electronically insulating, and mechanically robust to accommodate the volume changes of Si during cycling [13–16].

While various techniques exist for creating artificial SEI layers, dry coating technology offers a more sustainable and economical alternative to traditional wet methods [16,17]. Dry coating eliminates the

* Corresponding author at: Institute for Technical Thermodynamics, Technische Universität Darmstadt, Peter-Grünberg-Straße 10, Darmstadt, 64287, Germany.
E-mail address: ana-luisa.azevedo-costa@evonik.com (A.L.A. Costa).

Fig. 1. Schematic drawing of the dry coating process.

need for solvents and drying steps, reducing environmental impact and simplifying the manufacturing process [17–20].

This study investigates the potential of different nanostructured fumed metal oxides – TiO₂, MgO, ZrO₂, and Al₂O₃ – as coating agents for SiO_x/C anodes to enhance their electrochemical performance. Each metal oxide offers unique properties that can address specific challenges associated with Si-based anodes.

It was demonstrated that Al₂O₃ coatings significantly enhance electrochemical performance by improving mechanical integrity and reducing electrolyte decomposition [21–24]. TiO₂, with its excellent structural stability, environmental friendliness, and low cost, has gained attention as a promising anode material in its own right [25–27]. Its minimal volume changes during cycling (< 4%), fast lithium-ion kinetics, good capacity retention, and high Coulombic efficiency make it an attractive candidate [28]. Furthermore, the high working potential of TiO₂ (1.7 V vs. Li/Li⁺) enhances safety by suppressing dendrite formation and minimizing polarization effects [28]. However, its low electrical conductivity (10⁻¹² - 10⁻⁷ s cm⁻¹) and lithium-ion diffusion coefficient (10⁻¹⁵ - 10⁻⁹ cm² s⁻¹) can limit rate capability [27–29]. MgO coatings can help maintain the structural integrity of the composite during the significant volume expansion and contraction of Si, potentially safeguarding the active Si particles [30]. Moreover, the hydrophilic nature of MgO suggests its potential as a dehydrating agent, capable of preventing the hydrolysis of LiPF₆-based electrolytes. This could reduce the detrimental effects of HF, enhancing LIB stability and capacity retention [31,32]. Finally, ZrO₂ coatings have proven effective in suppressing SEI formation and shielding the active material from the electrolyte, particularly during the initial cycles, due to its exceptional dimensional and chemical stability [33,34]. This can lead to fewer side reactions, improved electron/ion transport, enhanced structural integrity, and ultimately, better rate capability and cycling performance [34–36].

While dry particle coating has demonstrated its effectiveness in enhancing the electrochemical performance of cathode materials [37], its impact on silicon-based anodes, which exhibit fundamentally different challenges related to volume expansion and SEI instability, remains largely unexplored. This work extends the application of dry coating technology to SiO_x/C anodes, systematically investigating the effects of different nanostructured fumed metal oxides on electrochemical performance. By leveraging the distinct properties of each metal oxide, we aim to mitigate silicon's intrinsic challenges while maintaining a scalable and solvent-free manufacturing approach. This study provides new insights into how dry-coated metal oxides influence interfacial chemistry and long-term cycling stability, bridging the gap between material design and practical implementation in next-generation LIBs.

2. Experimental

2.1. Sample preparation

Commercial SiO_x/C powder (HESO[®], AMPRIUS) and nanostructured fumed metal oxides (TiO₂: AEROXIDE[®] TiO₂ P 25, Evonik; MgO: VP MgO, Evonik; ZrO₂: VP ZrO₂, Evonik; Al₂O₃: AEROXIDE[®] Alu 130,

Evonik) were used as starting materials. Dry coating was performed using 100 g of powder in a high-energy mixer (Somakon MP-GL) with a volume of 0.5 L and two high-speed rotating rotors. The SiO_x/C powder was blended with 1 wt% of each nanostructured fumed metal oxide powder. The mixing procedure involved an initial phase at 500 rpm for 1 min to ensure homogeneous distribution, followed by an increase to 2000 rpm for 6 min to deagglomerate the nanostructured particles and facilitate their adherence to the SiO_x/C surface.

2.2. Sample characterization

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) with Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX)

Morphology and elemental composition of particles and electrodes before and after cycling were analyzed using a JSM-7600 F SEM from Jeol. The accelerating voltage was set to 1 kV, and the beam current was 30 pA. Samples were attached to sample holders using graphite tape. EDX measurements were performed with an X-Max 150 mm² detector (Oxford Instruments) and processed using Aztec software. For EDX analysis, the accelerating voltage and beam current were increased to 20 kV and 500 pA, respectively. Cross-sections of cycled electrodes were prepared for the analysis by embedding them in an organic resin and cutting them using microtomy.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) Cross-sectional lamellae were prepared using a focused ion beam (FIB) milling technique with a FEI Helios 650 dual-beam instrument. Samples were analyzed in both uncoated and coated states, with the coating consisting of 1 wt% of the respective fumed metal oxide. TEM images were acquired using a JEOL 2100 Plus electron microscope operated at 200 kV in monochromated mode.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (NMR) DMSO-d₆ was used as the solvent for NMR analysis. Fluorine (¹⁹F) and phosphorus-NMR (³¹P) spectra were referenced using external standards of H₃PO₃ (0 ppm) and F₆C₆ (2164.9 ppm) in DMSO-60.

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) The samples were prepared in a glovebox under dry nitrogen and evacuated to 10⁻⁸ mbar before measurement. XPS analysis was conducted on a Thermo Fisher Scientific ESCALAB 250xi system using an Al K α excitation source. The measurement spot diameter was 650 μ m, and the resolution was generally 0.1 eV.

X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were conducted using a Cubix³ Pharma diffractometer from Malvern Panalytical. The analysis utilized Cu-K α radiation to examine the crystal structure of the powders over a 2 θ range of 5 ° to 100 °.

2.3. Anode and cell preparation

Dry-coated SiO_x/C powder served as the active anode material, while Super C65 carbon black (CB, TIMCAL) and single-wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT, TUBALL[™] BATT H₂O 0.4%) served as conductive agents. Na-CMC (sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, Alfa Aesar) was employed as binder, with water as the solvent. A slurry was formulated by combining Si powder, conductive additives, and binder in a weight

ratio of 80:10:10 using a planetary centrifugal mixer. The slurries were cast onto copper foil using a doctor blading coater to create electrodes. After drying at room temperature and then at 80 °C for 30 min, the electrodes were further dried in a vacuum oven at 110 °C overnight. The active material loading was 2.2 mAh cm⁻², assuming a specific capacity of 1400 mAh g⁻¹. CR2032-type coin cells (MTI Corporation) were assembled in an argon-filled glove box using a 1 molar LiPF₆ solution in ethylene carbonate and ethyl methyl carbonate (50:50 wt:wt, Sigma-Aldrich) as the electrolyte. NMC811 (NEI Corporation) served as the counter electrode, and Celgard 2500 was used as the separator.

2.4. Cell cycling

Galvanostatic cycling was conducted between 3.0–4.2 V vs. Li⁺/Li for full-cells in a Maccor 4000 series battery cycler. The C rate was progressively increased every five cycles, starting from 0.1/0.1 (charge/discharge) and progressing to 0.2/0.2, 0.5/0.5, 1.0/1.0, and 1.0/2.0 C. Following this rate-cycling evaluation, the cells were further cycled at 1.0/1.0 C for an additional 75 cycles.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Dry-coating process

Dry coating is a versatile technique for creating composite particles by adhering fine “guest” particles (typically 0.1–50 μm) to the surface of larger “host” particles (1–500 μm) [20,38–40]. This adhesion is primarily governed by interparticle forces, particularly van der Waals forces, which become dominant at the nanoscale [17,41]. However, achieving a uniform and stable coating requires overcoming the natural tendency of guest particles to aggregate due to cohesive forces.

The dry coating process employs high-energy mixing to break apart guest particle agglomerates and promote their uniform distribution on the host particle surface. As the host and guest particles are subjected to intense mechanical agitation within the mixer, shear forces, particle-particle collisions, and impact energy work together to disrupt cohesive forces, effectively deagglomerating the guest particles. Once dispersed, these particles adhere to the host surface primarily through van der Waals interactions [42–45]. The efficiency of this adhesion process depends on several factors, including the surface energy and roughness of both the host and guest particles, as well as their relative size ratios. Smaller guest particles exhibit stronger adhesion due to their increased surface contact area and enhanced van der Waals attraction [17,20]. A schematic representation of the dry coating process is shown in Fig. 1. During mixing, the kinetic energy imparted to the system must be carefully controlled to balance effective deagglomeration with gentle deposition of the guest particles onto the host surface, preventing excessive damage to the host material. The final coating uniformity and stability are governed by key processing parameters, including rotation speed, mixing time, and impact intensity.

Dry coating methods offer several advantages over traditional wet coating techniques. By eliminating the need for solvents and drying steps, they significantly reduce environmental impact while streamlining the manufacturing process [17,20,39–41,46]. This translates to lower production costs, reduced processing time, and a smaller environmental footprint, making dry coating particularly attractive for large-scale industrial applications. In this study, SiO_x/C host particles were coated with nanostructured fumed metal oxides (TiO₂, MgO, ZrO₂, and Al₂O₃) synthesized via flame hydrolysis. This synthesis method inherently produces nanostructured aggregates with chemical and sintering bonds [38,47]. As a result, the high-energy mixing process must be carefully optimized to apply sufficient mechanical force to break apart these aggregates while preserving the structural integrity of the SiO_x/C host particles. The ability to fine-tune dry coating parameters offers a distinct advantage in tailoring coating morphology, thickness, and adhesion properties — key factors in enhancing electrochemical performance for lithium-ion battery applications.

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of SiO_x/C uncoated and coated with 1 wt% fumed TiO₂, MgO, ZrO₂ and Al₂O₃.

3.2. Analysis of coated anode material

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of uncoated and coated SiO_x/C materials are shown in Fig. 2. The diffraction peaks at 28.4°, 47.3° and 56.2° can be indexed as (111), (220) and (311) lattice orientation of silicon oxide (SiO_x) (JCPDS No. 00-030-1127), respectively. Additionally, diffraction peaks at 26.6°, 32.9°, 38.4°, 58.8°, and 72.5° correspond to the (111), (311), (002), (330), and (332) crystal planes of lithium metasilicate (Li₂SiO₃) (JCPDS No. 01-070-0330), indicating pre-lithiation of the anode material. A comparison of these diffraction patterns reveals no significant differences, confirming that the coating process does not alter the bulk crystalline structure of the anode material. Furthermore, the absence of additional diffraction peaks suggests that the coating material is either amorphous or present at concentrations below the detection limit of the XRD equipment.

3.3. Characterization of coating layer

To investigate the influence of surface modification, SiO_x/C composites were coated with 1 wt% of TiO₂, MgO, ZrO₂, and Al₂O₃. Cross-sectional Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) was employed to characterize the resulting morphology and structure of each material (Fig. 3). TEM images of uncoated SiO_x/C reveal SiO_x particles loosely embedded in the carbon matrix with limited interfacial contact, which may promote particle agglomeration and detachment during electrochemical cycling, potentially contributing to capacity fade. Moreover, the weak interfacial bonding could impede efficient electron transport within the electrode. TEM analysis of the coated materials (Fig. 3b–c) provided information on coating distribution, porosity, and layer uniformity, enabling an evaluation of the relationship between surface characteristics and coating morphology. In all coated samples, the coatings consisted of aggregated nanoparticles composed of smaller primary particles, forming a partially porous layer on the SiO_x/C surface that allows for electrolyte penetration and lithium-ion diffusion. The absence of large agglomerates in the coated samples suggests that the dry-coating process effectively dispersed the nanoparticle clusters. The resulting coatings were not continuous, densely packed layers,

Fig. 3. TEM image of cross-sections of a SiO_x/C particle (a) uncoated and coated with 1 wt% of (b) TiO_2 ; (c) MgO ; (d) ZrO_2 ; (e) Al_2O_3 .

Table 1

BET surface area of the different powder materials used in this study.

Sample	BET surface area (m^2/g)	Standard deviation
SiO_x/C	1.1	± 0.2
$\text{TiO}_2 @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	1.4	± 0.1
$\text{MgO} @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	2.2	± 0.2
$\text{ZrO}_2 @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	1.4	± 0.1
$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	1.9	± 0.2

Table 2

Calculated density of the different electrodes.

Sample	Density (g/cm^3)
SiO_x/C	1.21
$\text{TiO}_2 @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	1.12
$\text{MgO} @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	0.95
$\text{ZrO}_2 @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	1.21
$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	1.21

and the underlying SiO_x/C structure remained intact after mixing. The increased porosity of the coated SiO_x/C materials compared to the uncoated material was confirmed by Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) surface area measurements (Table 1).

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images (Fig. 4) show the surface morphology of the SiO_x/C composite, both uncoated (a) and coated with TiO_2 (b), MgO (c), ZrO_2 (d), and Al_2O_3 (e). The pristine SiO_x/C exhibits a smooth, clean surface with some protruding rough particles. The SEM images of the coated surfaces demonstrate the distribution of the coating materials. In all coated samples, a uniform coating distribution was achieved, while still exposing a significant portion of the active material surface.

To further examine the influence of nanostructured metal oxide coatings on elemental distribution, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) mapping was performed on each coated material (Fig. 5). Elemental mapping provides insights into particle interaction, powder dispersion, and coating quality. The TiO_2 (a) and Al_2O_3 (d) coatings exhibited relatively uniform distributions of the mapped metal element, without large agglomerates, indicating successful deagglomeration during the dry-coating process. In contrast, the MgO (b) and

ZrO_2 (c) coatings showed more heterogeneous distributions with areas of varying concentration. A uniform distribution is expected to enhance electrochemical stability, whereas a heterogeneous distribution could lead to variations in performance. As presented in Fig. 5e–h, the metal element corresponding to each coating (Ti, Mg, Zr, or Al) was clearly detected and mapped. While elements such as O, Na, and Si were present in the overall EDX spectra and composition tables, their spatial distribution was not directly mapped in this analysis. Therefore, observations of coating uniformity are based on the distribution of the mapped metal signal, which serves as a proxy for coating dispersion across the sample.

The electrode microstructure, governed by the distribution of active material on the current collector, is crucial for optimizing cell performance [48–52]. To assess this, cross-sections of electrodes fabricated with TiO_2 -, MgO -, ZrO_2 -, and Al_2O_3 -coated SiO_x/C active materials were analyzed using SEM-EDX (Fig. 6). A comparison of BSE images with EDX mappings of the coating metals confirms that the coating layer remains intact for all fumed metal oxides, consistently covering individual anode active material particles. Cross-sectional images further show that the coatings are well-distributed and remain attached to the active material, indicating that the particle structure was preserved throughout the slurry preparation process.

To assess the presence of voids within the electrode structure that could accommodate silicon expansion during cycling, electrode density measurements were performed (Table 2). A lower electrode density suggests a higher volume fraction of void space, which could provide room for the volumetric expansion of silicon during lithiation, potentially reducing mechanical stress and improving cycle life. Conversely, a higher electrode density indicates a more compact structure with less space for silicon expansion, which could lead to increased stress and, ultimately, capacity fade. The uncoated SiO_x/C electrode exhibited a density of $1.21 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$. The MgO coating resulted in a noticeable decrease in electrode density to $0.95 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$, suggesting the introduction of more void space within the electrode structure. This increased void volume could provide more accommodation for silicon expansion during cycling, potentially leading to reduced mechanical stress and an improvement in cycle stability. In contrast, the TiO_2 , ZrO_2 , and Al_2O_3 coatings resulted in slightly lower or similar densities compared to the uncoated SiO_x/C , with values around 1.12 – $1.21 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$. These

Fig. 4. SEM images of the surfaces of SiO₂/C (a) uncoated and coated with 1 wt% of (b) TiO₂; (c) MgO; (d) ZrO₂; (e) Al₂O₃.

Fig. 5. EDX mappings (top) and elemental distribution (bottom) of SiO₂/C coated with 1 wt% of (a, e) TiO₂ (Ti), (b, f) MgO (Mg), (c, g) ZrO₂ (Zr), and (d, h) Al₂O₃ (Al).

smaller changes suggest that these coatings did not significantly alter the overall packing density of the electrode. Interestingly, a more compact electrode structure (as seen in TiO₂, ZrO₂, and Al₂O₃ coatings) could enhance electronic conductivity, but if the electrode is too dense without sufficient void space for silicon expansion, it might be more prone to cracking and stress during cycling, leading to capacity fade over time.

3.4. Particle interaction with electrolyte

LiPF₆-based electrolytes are widely employed in commercial lithium-ion batteries due to their high ionic conductivity and reasonable electrochemical stability. However, these advantages are counterbalanced by significant challenges, primarily arising from the hygroscopic nature of LiPF₆. This sensitivity to moisture leads to rapid

decomposition upon exposure to even trace amounts of water, generating highly reactive and corrosive by-products such as POF₃, PF₅, and HF. These degradation products contribute to the deterioration of the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer, solvent degradation, and even the dissolution of transition metals from the cathode [53–55]. The decomposition of LiPF₆ begins with its hydrolysis, as outlined in the following reaction [56,57]:

Subsequently, the phosphorus pentafluoride (PF₅) interacts with water, generating hydrofluoric acid (HF) and phosphoryl fluoride (POF₃) [58]:

These reactions trigger further instability in the electrolyte, promoting undesirable interactions with solvent molecules. Ethylene carbonate

Fig. 6. BSE images (left) and corresponding EDX mapping (right) of cross-sections of electrodes manufactured with SiO_x/C (a) uncoated and coated with 1 wt% of (b,c) TiO_2 ; (d,e) MgO ; (f,g) ZrO_2 ; (h,i) Al_2O_3 .

(EC), a common electrolyte solvent, undergoes ring-opening polymerization in the presence of PF_5 , producing polyethylene-like structures and generating CO_2 gas. Similarly, diethyl carbonate (DEC) reacts with both HF and PF_5 , leading to additional HF and CO_2 gas formation [59–61]:

The accumulation of HF within the electrolyte is particularly problematic. Not only does it deplete electrolyte components, but it also aggressively attacks electrode surfaces. The SEI layer, which plays a crucial role in stabilizing lithium-ion batteries, is especially vulnerable to HF-induced degradation. As this protective layer deteriorates, it leads to increased lithium consumption, capacity fade, and a reduction in overall battery lifespan [62]. Another major challenge is the dissolution of electrode materials, which not only results in the loss of active material but also accelerates cell aging. During prolonged cycling, dissolved

Table 3

HF and PF_6^- content in each sample after interacting with electrolyte measured by NMR.

Compound	Mol [%]	
	HF	PF_6^-
Electrolyte reference	6.7	90.2
Uncoated SiO_x/C	42.7	0.7
$\text{TiO}_2 @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	33.2	28.6
$\text{MgO} @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	51.0	7.9
$\text{ZrO}_2 @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	40.6	8.1
$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 @ \text{SiO}_x/\text{C}$	4.5	82.3

transition metal oxides from the cathode migrate and redeposit onto the anode surface. This leads to an increase in cell impedance and a progressive loss of capacity [63–65]. A commonly reported degradation pathway involves a multi-step process where electrolyte salt decomposition generates HF, which subsequently corrodes the metal oxides, further exacerbating battery instability [63,66]. To mitigate these challenges, various metal oxide coatings, including TiO_2 , MgO , ZrO_2 , and Al_2O_3 , have been explored for their potential protective roles. TiO_2 , ZrO_2 , and Al_2O_3 coatings are known to neutralize HF through direct reactions, while MgO acts as a dehydrating agent, preventing the hydrolysis of LiPF_6 and thus reducing HF formation [31,32,67,68]. Al_2O_3 has shown particular promise in inhibiting HF accumulation and enhancing electrolyte stability [53,63,66]. This mechanism occurs through a combination of HF scavenging, passivation layer formation, and electrolyte stabilization. The reaction between Al_2O_3 and HF follows:

Through this reaction, Al_2O_3 actively consumes HF, reducing its concentration in the electrolyte and preventing further degradation of the SEI layer. The formation of AlF_3 serves as a passivation layer, which has been shown to facilitate Li^+ transport, ensuring a more uniform and stable SEI, preventing continued electrolyte decomposition and minimizing further HF interactions with active battery components [69, 70].

To quantify the extent of electrolyte degradation, ^{19}F and ^{31}P NMR spectroscopy were used to measure HF content in each sample, as well as PF_6^- concentrations to assess the electrolyte's decomposition state. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Exposure of uncoated SiO_x/C to the reference electrolyte leads to a significant increase in HF content from 6.7% to 42.7%, indicating a strong catalytic effect on electrolyte decomposition. However, the introduction of Al_2O_3 coating dramatically reduces HF content to 4.5%, showcasing its exceptional ability to suppress HF formation. In contrast, other metal oxide coatings exhibit moderate benefits, with TiO_2 reducing HF content to 33.2%, and MgO and ZrO_2 showing limited impact. In terms of electrolyte stability, the uncoated SiO_x/C results in a drastic reduction of PF_6^- content from 90.2% to 0.7%, signifying severe electrolyte degradation. The introduction of Al_2O_3 coating preserves PF_6^- at 82.3%, nearly restoring the electrolyte to its original state. TiO_2 also exhibits a notable improvement, increasing PF_6^- to 28.6%, whereas MgO and ZrO_2 show only minor enhancements. Maintaining a high PF_6^- concentration is crucial for minimizing gas generation within the cell and ensuring long-term electrochemical performance. The results strongly indicate that Al_2O_3 coating, and to a lesser extent TiO_2 , not only mitigate HF accumulation but also significantly improve electrolyte stability. This highlights the potential of surface coatings as an effective strategy to enhance lithium-ion battery durability and efficiency.

3.5. Electrochemical characterization

The electrochemical performance of SiO_x/C electrodes coated with various metal oxides (TiO_2 , MgO , ZrO_2 , and Al_2O_3) was assessed

Fig. 7. Cycling performance of SiO_x/C anode uncoated and coated with 1wt % of different metal oxides (average of three cells for each material, using NMC 811 as counter-electrode): (a) Rate capability, (b) Coulombic efficiency and (c) normalized discharge capacity.

through a protocol involving progressively increasing C-rates every five cycles. The initial C-rate was 0.1/0.1 (charge/discharge), then increased stepwise to 0.2/0.2, 0.5/0.5, 1.0/1.0, and finally 1.0/2.0 C before returning to 1.0/1.0 C. Fig. 7 illustrates the results of this evaluation, including the specific discharge capacity (normalized to the mass of SiO_x/C), Coulombic efficiency, and normalized discharge capacity for each electrode.

As shown in Fig. 7a, all samples experienced a gradual decrease in discharge capacity, even at constant C-rate over five cycles, likely due to limitations in lithium-ion diffusion within the active material. However, the coated anodes consistently outperformed the uncoated SiO_x/C at all current densities, highlighting the positive impact of the coatings on rate capability.

Examining the cycling stability at different C-rates provides additional insights. When the C-rate was reduced from 2.0 C to 1.0 C after 25 cycles, the Al₂O₃ and ZrO₂ coatings exhibited the highest capacity retention. Although the ZrO₂-coated electrode initially demonstrated lower capacity than the Al₂O₃-coated electrode, it exhibited minimal capacity fade in the early cycles (Fig. 7c), eventually achieving similar

capacity levels. However, over extended cycling, the Al₂O₃ coating provided the most effective capacity retention, whereas both MgO and ZrO₂ exhibited accelerated capacity fading. While TiO₂ exhibited lower initial capacity, it demonstrated superior long-term stability, ranking second in capacity after 100 cycles.

Further analysis of electrochemical data (Fig. 7b) indicates that the uncoated electrode exhibited a lower initial Coulombic efficiency (ICE) compared to the coated samples, suggesting higher irreversible capacity loss in the initial cycles. This may be attributed to increased SEI layer formation and particle cracking in the absence of a protective coating. The metal oxide coatings mitigated these detrimental effects by reducing direct interaction between SiO_x/C and the electrolyte, thereby preserving the structural integrity of the electrode.

The porosity of the coating layer is an important parameter influencing the rate performance of coated anodes. This can be related to the BET surface area of each material, presented in Table 1. Assuming that the liquid electrolyte penetrates the porous coating layer, we suggest that the porosity of the coating can influence lithium transport across the layer, in addition to the intrinsic lithium diffusion properties of the metal oxides. However, while MgO exhibited the highest

Fig. 8. Galvanostatic charge–discharge profiles (3.0 – 4.2 V, room temperature): (a) First cycle, all samples; (b–f) Subsequent cycles at various current densities for: (b) Uncoated, (c) TiO_2 , (d) MgO , (e) ZrO_2 , (f) Al_2O_3 -coated SiO_x/C .

porosity ($2.2 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), it did not provide a significant improvement in HF neutralization or electrolyte stability (Table 1). In contrast, Al_2O_3 demonstrated both high porosity ($1.9 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) and beneficial chemical reactivity, effectively neutralizing HF and preserving PF_6^- content. This can explain its superior electrochemical performance relative to the other coatings. Although ZrO_2 and TiO_2 exhibited similar porosity levels, the TiO_2 -coated samples displayed superior rate performance. This enhanced stability can be attributed to TiO_2 's improved ability to mitigate HF formation and maintain electrolyte stability, as evidenced by its higher PF_6^- content and lower HF levels when compared to ZrO_2 .

Among all coatings, Al_2O_3 demonstrated the most pronounced protective effect on the active material surface, likely due to its chemical nature and uniform coating morphology. The Al_2O_3 -coated electrode consistently exhibited superior rate capability, Coulombic efficiency, and capacity retention, suggesting that it serves as an effective barrier against side reactions in SiO_x/C electrodes, while allowing for the liquid electrolyte to penetrate the porous coating layer. It is important to acknowledge that the coating mass fraction can significantly influence electrochemical performance. While this study utilized a consistent coating mass fraction of 1 wt% for all samples to facilitate comparison, previous work [71] has shown that the optimal coating amount may vary for different metal oxides. Further investigation is needed to optimize the coating parameters for each material and fully exploit their potential for enhancing the performance of SiO_x/C anodes.

Fig. 8 presents the voltage profiles of the charge and discharge curves of SiO_x/C anodes at various cycles (3rd, 8th, 13th, 18th, and 23rd) under different current densities ranging from 0.1 C to 2.0 C, cycled between 3.0 and 4.2 V. Fig. 8a shows the initial charge and discharge voltage profiles of SiO_x/C anodes: uncoated and coated with 1 wt% of TiO_2 , MgO , ZrO_2 , and Al_2O_3 . While most samples exhibit similar behavior, the Al_2O_3 coating demonstrates a first charge curve at a lower voltage, suggesting reduced resistance and potentially facilitating initial lithium insertion. Additionally, the first discharge curve of the Al_2O_3 -coated anode occurs at a higher voltage than the others, indicating enhanced lithium extraction. This suggests improved electronic conductivity within the electrode or a more favorable interaction between lithium ions and the coated SiO_x/C surface. Furthermore, a comparison of first-cycle Coulombic efficiencies reveals that the Al_2O_3 -coated sample exhibits the lowest irreversible capacity loss.

Upon cycling, the capacity of uncoated SiO_x/C (Fig. 8b) decreases at a faster rate than that of TiO_2 (8c), MgO (8d), ZrO_2 (8e), and Al_2O_3 (8f). Additionally, a voltage drop at the beginning of each discharge step increases with cycle number. The uncoated SiO_x/C anode (Fig. 8b) experiences the most significant capacity fade, particularly after the initial cycles, highlighting the challenge of maintaining structural integrity in bare SiO_x/C during repeated lithium insertion and extraction. In contrast, the Al_2O_3 -coated material exhibits significantly improved capacity retention, emphasizing the positive impact of the coating on the long-term cycling stability of the anode. This superior performance, compared to other coatings, can be attributed to its ability to neutralize HF and protect the electrolyte from degradation. Electrolyte decomposition on the electrode surface leads to capacity degradation and an increase in charge transfer resistance, contributing to capacity fading.

3.6. Analytical characterization of cycled electrodes

Backscattered electron (BSE) imaging was utilized to examine the morphology of cycled electrodes and differentiate Si-based particles from the surrounding matrix. In the BSE image of the coated electrode (Fig. 9), SiO_x/C particles remain largely intact even after 100 cycles. A layer of electrolyte decomposition products, contributing to the formation of the solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI), was observed on the surface of all electrodes post-cycling. The SEI is a crucial passivation layer that forms on the anode during the initial cycles and significantly influences ion transport, electrode degradation, and electrolyte consumption. Understanding its composition and stability is vital for optimizing battery performance, cycle life, and safety.

SEM-EDX mapping was used to investigate the distribution and integrity of the metal oxide coatings after cycling. The EDX mapping of Al (Fig. 9i) confirms that the Al_2O_3 coating remains stable and intact on the anode particle surface after extensive cycling, demonstrating the robustness of the coating not only during the slurry preparation and anode manufacturing but also throughout the battery's cycling process. However, other electrodes did not retain their coatings in the same manner. In comparison to pre-cycling characterization (Fig. 6), secondary components between SiO_x/C particles were more apparent, likely due to electrolyte decomposition and the formation of the SEI.

Fig. 9. After cycling BSE images (left) and corresponding EDX mapping (right) of cross-sections of electrodes manufactured with SiO_x/C (a) uncoated and coated with 1 wt% of (b,c) TiO_2 ; (d,e) MgO ; (f,g) ZrO_2 ; (h,i) Al_2O_3 .

This led to increased impedance, performance degradation, and capacity fade. The absence of detectable coating material after cycling suggests that some coatings may have dissolved into the electrolyte, reacted to form new compounds within the SEI, or detached due to the mechanical stresses from the expansion and contraction of the SiO_x/C particles. Additionally, the formation of a thick SEI layer could obscure the coating material, making it undetectable in post-cycling EDX analysis.

SEM imaging of post-cycled electrodes (Fig. 10) further reveals notable differences in surface morphology depending on the presence and type of metal oxide coating. Consistent with BSE analysis, the bulk of the SiO_x/C particles remains intact after 100 cycles, indicating structural stability. However, distinct variations in surface features emerge post-cycling, suggesting differences in SEI formation and coating stability. The uncoated electrode and those coated with TiO_2 , MgO , and ZrO_2 exhibit prominent secondary deposits, suggesting that these coatings may have either reacted with electrolyte species, undergone partial dissolution, or influenced the formation of a modified SEI layer.

Fig. 10. SEM images before (left) and after (right) cycling of the surface of electrode manufactured with SiO_x/C (a, b) uncoated and coated with 1 wt% of (c, d) TiO_2 ; (e, f) MgO ; (g, h) ZrO_2 ; (i, j) Al_2O_3 .

In contrast, the Al_2O_3 -coated electrode shows minimal new surface deposits, indicating that it effectively suppresses excessive electrolyte decomposition and stabilizes SEI growth.

These observations align with the electrode thickness measurements, where significant differences were observed in the volumetric expansion between coated and uncoated SiO_x/C electrodes. The uncoated electrode exhibited a 62% increase in thickness, which can be attributed to substantial SEI growth due to electrolyte decomposition and side reactions. In contrast, the metal oxide coatings effectively mitigated expansion. The Al_2O_3 coating provided the best suppression, limiting expansion to just 3%, suggesting superior protection against side reactions and SEI growth, as previously demonstrated by the lower amount of HF and conservation of PF_6^- in the electrolyte. ZrO_2 , MgO , and TiO_2 coatings also contributed to a reduction in electrode expansion, with values of 42%, 15%, and 12.2%, respectively. These results suggest that while the coatings do not directly impact the expansion of the SiO_x/C anode particles, they significantly reduce electrode thickness growth by limiting side reactions and controlling SEI development.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was employed to further investigate the impact of the metal oxide coatings on the chemistry of

Fig. 11. Li 1s, C 1s, O 1s and F 1s detailed spectra of cycled electrodes containing SiO_2/C uncoated and coated with TiO_2 , MgO , ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 .

the anodes after 100 cycles. Fig. 11 presents the Li 1s, C 1s, O 1s, and F 1s core-level spectra obtained from the cycled anodes with different metal oxide coatings. This analysis aims to provide insights into the surface chemistry and composition of the SEI layer formed on the different electrodes, elucidating the role of the coatings in modifying the SEI properties and enhancing electrochemical performance.

The Li 1s spectra reveal four distinct components, with binding energies ranging from 54.9 eV to 56.8 eV, attributable to various lithium compounds: LiOH (54.9 eV), Li_2CO_3 (55.1–55.2 eV), Li_2O (55.6 eV), and LiF (55.7–56.8 eV).

The Al_2O_3 -coated anode was the only one exhibiting the peak for the LiF component, indicating that the coating promotes the formation of a LiF-rich SEI. LiF possesses a high shear modulus (55.14 GPa), which helps the SEI withstand the significant volume changes that occur during cycling, especially in silicon-based anodes [72–75]. This property helps to prevent cracking and delamination of the SEI layer, thereby contributing to the long-term stability and performance of the anode. Additionally, molecular dynamics simulations have provided varying estimates for the energy barrier of lithium-ion migration in LiF, with reported values ranging from 0.55 to 0.65 eV [76,77], which are

lower than those of other SEI components. This suggests that LiF could facilitate Li^+ diffusion kinetics and enhance interfacial charge transfer. However, other studies have reported a higher migration energy barrier of 0.729 eV [76,78], highlighting the complexity of lithium transport in LiF-containing SEIs. Nevertheless, previous studies [79] have demonstrated that an engineered multicomponent SEI, containing controlled proportions of LiF and Li_2CO_3 , exhibit unique interfacial effects that enhance ionic conductivity. The authors found that the interfaces between nanocrystalline LiF and Li_2CO_3 grains generate space-charge effects, leading to a localized enrichment of charge carriers and improving overall ion transport within the SEI [26,79]. Additionally, LiF contributes to SEI stability, as fluorine atoms within LiF form strong bonds with lithium ethylene dicarbonate, reinforcing the SEI structure with a “glue effect” [76,80]. Overall, establishing a LiF-rich inorganic layer has been recognized as an effective strategy for enhancing SEI stability, minimizing lithium consumption, and ultimately extending battery cycle life [76,81,82].

The formation of LiF in the SEI layer is critically influenced by the interaction between the Al_2O_3 coating and HF produced from electrolyte decomposition. Due to its high reactivity with HF, Al_2O_3 promotes HF neutralization, thereby protecting the SEI layer's stability and enhancing overall battery performance. Specifically, HF reacts with Al_2O_3 , according to Eq. (5), forming AlF_3 and water. AlF_3 is stable and does not engage in further side reactions, unlike HF, which can disrupt the SEI structure and cause electrode degradation. During this process, fluoride ions (F^-) are released, which then react with lithium ions in the electrolyte to form LiF on the anode surface. Thus, this “HF scavenging” mechanism by Al_2O_3 not only improves the stability of the SEI but also promotes the formation of a LiF-rich SEI, which is beneficial for battery performance. In contrast, other metal oxides show weaker reactivity with HF, resulting in less efficient LiF formation.

On the other hand, the LiOH and Li_2CO_3 peaks, associated with less desirable SEI components that can lead to increased impedance and capacity fade, are not detected in the Al_2O_3 -coated anode. LiOH can be formed due to water contamination or degradation processes, while Li_2CO_3 is generally considered decomposition product of electrolyte components reacting with lithium [83–89].

Analysis of the C 1s spectra reveals differences in the composition and relative abundance of carbon-containing species within the electrode. The interpretation of the C 1s XPS spectrum is complex due to the overlapping contributions from various sources within the electrode, including electrolyte decomposition products, carbonaceous SEI components, the polymeric binder, and the carbon additive. A prominent peak at ≈ 285 eV, observed for all electrodes, is attributed to C–C bonds within the SuperP conductive carbon [72]. This peak exhibits a higher intensity for the electrode with the Al_2O_3 -coated SiO_x/C anode material. The TiO_2 -coated anode exhibits a slightly lower carbonate peak compared to the other coatings and the uncoated anode, while the Al_2O_3 -coated anode does not show a distinct peak. This indicates that Al_2O_3 effectively suppresses carbonate formation, with TiO_2 also contributing to a lesser extent, thereby reducing electrolyte decomposition. The peaks at 285–287 eV and 287–288 eV are possibly related to C–O and G–O environments in the CMC binder, respectively. The G–O, C–O, and C–C components, associated with organic species within the SEI, are most prominent on the Al_2O_3 -coated anode. This could be attributed to the Al_2O_3 coating promoting the formation of a more stable and polymeric SEI layer.

The O 1s core peaks at 531–532 eV and 533–534 eV can be attributed to G=O, C–O–C and C–OH, respectively. These functionalities are associated with the binder material. The uncoated anode does not show a distinct C–OH peak, whereas the C–OH component is most intense on the Al_2O_3 -coated anode. This suggests a higher presence of hydroxyl groups, indicating that the binder's integrity is better preserved in the presence of Al_2O_3 . The G=O, C–O–C component is similar across all samples.

The F 1s core peaks observed at 687 eV and 685–687 eV correspond to $\text{Li}_x\text{PO}_y\text{F}_z$ and LiF, respectively. $\text{Li}_x\text{PO}_y\text{F}_z$ is associated with the decomposition of the LiPF_6 electrolyte salt, forming products such as $\text{Li}_x\text{PF}_y/\text{Li}_x\text{PO}_y\text{F}_z$ [90,91]. The intensity of the $\text{Li}_x\text{PO}_y\text{F}_z$ component is similar for all the coated anodes and higher than that of the uncoated and Al_2O_3 -coated anode active material. Consistent with the Li 1s spectra, the LiF component in the F 1s spectra is most prominent on the Al_2O_3 -coated anode, further supporting the claim of a LiF-rich SEI layer on this electrode.

The XPS analysis provides compelling evidence that the Al_2O_3 coating significantly alters the SEI composition on the Si anode. The formation of a LiF-rich SEI, along with the suppression of detrimental LiOH/ Li_2CO_3 and carbonate species, contributes to improved SEI stability and ionic conductivity. This is consistent with the observed enhanced electrochemical performance of the Al_2O_3 -coated anode. The other metal oxide coatings also show some influence on the SEI composition, but their effects are less pronounced than those of Al_2O_3 .

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the feasibility and effectiveness of dry particle coating with nanostructured fumed metal oxides as a promising approach to enhance the electrochemical performance of SiO_x/C anodes for lithium-ion batteries. The dry coating process, a sustainable and scalable technique, successfully disperses metal oxide nanoparticles onto the SiO_x/C surface, forming a protective layer that addresses key challenges associated with Si-based anodes, such as poor cycling stability, large volumetric expansion, and electrolyte decomposition.

Among the metal oxides investigated (TiO_2 , MgO, ZrO_2 , and Al_2O_3), Al_2O_3 demonstrated the most pronounced enhancement in electrochemical performance. The Al_2O_3 -coated anode exhibited superior cycling stability, rate capability, and Coulombic efficiency compared to both the uncoated SiO_x/C and other coated samples. This enhanced performance can be attributed to several synergistic factors that collectively mitigate the detrimental effects of Si-based anodes.

The coating's porous structure, observed through transmission electron microscopy (TEM), increases the number of available active sites for lithium-ion storage, facilitating improved ion diffusion kinetics and higher electrolyte accessibility, thereby contributing to enhanced rate capability. Additionally, the uniform distribution of the coatings prevents direct contact between the active material (SiO_x/C) and the electrolyte, minimizing parasitic reactions and enhancing Coulombic efficiency. Notably, the Al_2O_3 coating not only reduced volumetric expansion but also helped suppress side reactions that typically lead to SEI growth and electrolyte decomposition, by minimizing the formation of HF while maintaining electrolyte stability.

Furthermore, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) revealed significant differences in the surface chemistry of the SEI layer. The Al_2O_3 coating promoted the formation of a more stable and conductive SEI, rich in LiF, while reducing undesirable components such as LiOH and Li_2CO_3 , which are typically associated with increased impedance and capacity fade. LiF's high shear modulus helps withstand volume changes, and its ionic conductivity improves the overall cycle stability of the anode [72–75,85,92–94]. This favorable SEI composition is a key factor contributing to the superior electrochemical performance of the Al_2O_3 -coated anodes.

The findings of this study underscore the significant potential of dry particle coating with metal oxides, particularly Al_2O_3 , as an effective strategy for improving the electrochemical performance of Si-based anodes in next-generation LIBs. The enhanced properties of Al_2O_3 -coated SiO_x/C anodes – such as superior cycling stability, rate capability, and Coulombic efficiency – make them highly promising for use in high-performance LIBs. Future research should focus on optimizing coating parameters, such as coating thickness, particle size, and composition, to further enhance electrochemical performance and expand the applicability of this technique to other anode materials, potentially contributing to the development of next-generation, high-capacity lithium-ion batteries with improved cycle life and safety.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ana L. Azevedo Costa: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mareike Liebertseder:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Tatiana Gambaryan-Roisman:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Daniel Esken:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Frank Menzel:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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